

Development of Pultrusion System for Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites

Yoshitaka Tanaka, Naoyuki Shikamoto, Akio Ohtani, Asami Nakai, Hiroyuki Hamada
Division of Advanced Fibro Science, Kyoto Institute of Technology, Kyoto, Japan
[Yoshitaka Tanaka]: k5330049@edu.kit.ac.jp

SUMMARY

Pultrusion process is one of the composite production methods to be suitable for mass production, and by using this process a continuous production with uniform cross sections is maintained. In this study, pultrusion system for continuous carbon fiber reinforced polyamide66 composites (CF/PA66) were developed.

Keywords: pultrusion, braiding, thermoplastic, continuous fiber, impregnation

INTRODUCTION

Pultrusion process is one of the composite production methods to be suitable for mass production. However, there is little research for pultrusion of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite (CFRTP). Because, thermoplastic resin has so high melt viscosity that it is difficult to impregnate into the reinforcing fiber bundles. Two kinds of pultrusion products were molded by way of proposed system which is outlined below, one was unidirectional composite and the other was braided composite.

Micro Braided Yarn and Pultrusion Processing

In order to overcome the above-mentioned problem of CFRTP for impregnation, we have developed Micro-braided yarn (Fig.1). Tubular braiding machine was employed to produce Micro-braided yarns. The matrix resin fiber bundles are braided around a reinforcement fiber bundle.

Fig.1 Micro braided yarn

Pultrusion machine was mainly made up of mold, cooling equipment and drawing roll. The length of mold is 200 mm, and the shape is circular rod (diameter = 10 mm, in entrance $R = 40$ mm). The mold can control temperature separately at front and rear sections. The cooling equipment has three sections, in which water flow volume can be controlled separately.

Materials and Bending Method

A carbon fiber bundle (UT500 F301, 12000filaments, TOHO TENAX Co., Ltd.) as reinforcement and the PA66 resin fiber bundles (470dtex, TORAY Co., Ltd.) as matrix were used to fabricate Micro-braided Yarn (CF/PA66). 16 PA66 resin fiber bundles were braided around a carbon fiber bundle by using the tubular braiding machine. The volume fraction of carbon fiber was about 39%.

The specimen size was about 8.5 mm in diameter for 3-point bending test. The span length was about 130 mm. 3-point bending test was performed by using INSTRON Universal Testing Machine (Model 4206) at crosshead speed of 1.0 mm/min.

Results and Discussion

The result of bending test was shown in Table 1. From Table 1, it was clear that both the modulus and the strength of unidirectional composites were higher than that of braiding composites. The reason of this tendency is not only effect of volume fraction but also fracture mechanism from the result of cross sectional observation of specimens.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of each composite

	Bending modulus (GPa)	Bending strength (MPa)	Vf (%)
Uni	118	778	76.6
Braid	79	450	56.3

Braiding Pultrusion System

In this report, we made braided rod composite. There are several advantages in braided rod. For example, we can control the mechanical properties by controlling braiding angle. Moreover, we can insert the Micro-braided yarns straightly along the machine direction (MD) in order to increase the mechanical properties. However, the fabrication process was not continuous way. Our future work is to fabricate braided composite by connecting the braiding machine to pultrusion machine. The schematic diagram of this process is shown in Fig. 2. We called this process Braiding Pultrusion Molding for Thermoplastics “BPM-TP”.

Fig. 2 Schematic drawing of BPM-TP